

conditions. Its highest recorded yields are 5.2 t/ha under wetland and 2.9 t/ha under limited irrigation – superior to

those of the other varieties tested (see table). Red rice is preferred in southern Tamil Nadu. ■

A breakthrough in the ceiling grain yield of ponlai rice

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The grain yield per unit area of ponlai rice in Taiwan is said to have approached a ceiling; during the past decade the yield increase of elite entries in regional tests has been less than 5%. The incorporation of the semidwarf plant type into ponlai varieties is considered necessary for further yield increases.

The new variety Tainung 67 has given a breakthrough in grain yield. It probably inherited its semidwarf plant

type from Taichung Native 1 through a “bridge” variety, Taichung Shi 138 (later named Taichung 187).

Tainung 67, a selection from the cross Taichung Shi 138/2* Tainung 61, outyielded the control variety by 9% in the first crop and by 14% in the second crop in regional yield tests at 8 locations in Taiwan from 1977 to 1979. The variety is particularly adapted to Hsinchu, Tainan, and Taitung districts (see table). Its high yield potential was also confirmed in local trials in Taipei, Hsinchu, and Taichung districts. Tainung 67 showed a relatively low regression coefficient of entry means on environment means of grain yield in the regional yield tests (see

figure). A sister line, TNGY-WF5, showed an even lower regression coefficient, but with a lower yield potential.

The growth duration (transplanting to harvest) of Tainung 67 is about 120 days in the first crop and 100 days in the second. It is relatively lodging resistant and responsive to nitrogen fertilizer. In the uniform disease nurseries, Tainung 67 showed blast resistance similar to that of Tainan 5 and fair resistance to bacterial blight. It is relatively tolerant of the brown planthopper and sclerotial stem rot. Its milled rice quality meets local consumer requirements. In 1978 the new variety was planted in 101,000 ha in Taiwan, mostly in Hsinchu, Taichung, and Tainan districts. It is expected to be more widely planted in 1979. ■

Grain yield of Tainung 67 and percentage of yield increase over the control variety in 1977–79 regional tests at 8 locations in Taiwan.

Location	Tainung 67				Control variety
	1st crop yield (t/ha)	Increase (% over control)	2d crop yield (t/ha)	Increase (% over control)	
Taipei	6.0	7	4.7	8	Taipei 309
Hsinchu	5.2	15	4.8	22	Hsinchu 56
Taichung	7.4	8	6.0	18	Tainan 5
Tainan	1.0	13	4.5	20	Tainan 6
Kaohsiung	5.3	2	3.1	11	Kaohsiung 139
Taitung	5.7	20	4.9	23	Taitung 2 7
Hwalien	5.1	18	3.9	9	Tainan 5
Lotung	4.7	-4	3.7	5	Tainan 5

IR2053-206-1-3-6, a new rice variety for the Sudan Gezira

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The line IR2053-206-1-3-6 has performed well in field experiments and observational nurseries at the Gezira Research Station (GRS) from 1975 to 1978. The line, introduced from IRRI in 1975, is from the cross IR1416-131-5/IR22//C4-63. Its plant type, growth duration, yield, and grain quality are superior to those of the rices currently grown in the Gezira. At GRS, its yields were as high as 8.6 t/ha and averaged 6.9 t/ha in farmers' fields. GRS established direct seeding as the standard cultural practice for IR2053-206-1-3-6.

In an ARC meeting at Wad Medani on 20 February 1979, the Sudan Technical Subcommittee for Variety Release unanimously accepted the release of IR2053-206-1-3-6 as a rice variety for the Gezira. ■

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Grand mean yield (t/ha) of rough rice and regression coefficient (bi) of entry means of environment means of 14 entries in 1977II-1979I regional yield trials of ponlai japonica rice varieties at 8 locations in Taiwan. TNGY = Tainung yuh, CNY = Chianung yuh, TPY = Taipei yuh, HCY = Hsinchu yuh, TCY = Taichung yuh, NKY = Nankai yuh, KHY = Kaohsiung yuh, TTY = Taitung yuh, HLY = Hwalien yuh. Taiwan.